

Considerations when Developing Online Learning Environments

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Making the transition to an online or virtual or learning environment can be intimidating when adapting a traditional in-person course or training to a different instructional modality. Online and virtual learning environments provide the opportunity to create a broader space to attract a variety of students. Therefore, one must consider the cognitive diversity of the group when developing a courses structure, materials, and learning exercises. The following report provides an approach that I have successfully utilized to develop online courses with an emphasis to create an engaging atmosphere that facilitates learning through a community of practice among students.

Keywords— cognitive diversity, higher education, education, instruction, online education, courses, development, learning environments

I. INTRODUCTION

Making the transition to an online or virtual or learning environment can be intimidating when adapting a traditional in-person course or training to a different instructional modality. Online and virtual learning environments provide the opportunity to create a broader space to attract a variety of students. Therefore, one must consider the cognitive diversity of the group when developing a courses structure, materials, and learning exercises. The following report provides an approach that I have successfully utilized to develop online courses with an emphasis to create an engaging atmosphere that facilitates learning through a community of practice among students.

II. THE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT

Constructivist Approach

Prior to the development of content is to best understand which approach you want to adopt. There are a variety on consideration to account for such as content, audience, setting, and timeframe of your course or training. Based on my analysis of these factors I have and continue to use a constructivist approach for developing and conducting online courses. The primary reason this approach was selected is associated with the program's target audience. The intended target audience will consist of individuals that are graduate and post-graduate students. Based on the parameters of expectation and perceived experiences they would have it is expected that the program students will bring diverse backgrounds, thoughts, culture, education, insight, work experiences, and lived experiences which they will be expected to express in the online classroom. Following constructivist methods, I will serve as the facilitator of to help create collaborative learning spaces for uncovering insights

and building knowledge. It is highly anticipated that this incubator approach to learning will support and community of practice that will carry on beyond the course and into professionals and scholastic lives of the participants.

Learning Environment

The structure of the course will be centralized around the concept of fostering a flexible and engaging learning environment. As the globe has been impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic, expectations for interactions, engagement and learning have also evolved (e.g., streaming synchronously, virtual teams, remote work). It is projected that these social expectations will also infiltrate into the learning environment. Similarly, consumer behavior of media and information consumption has transitions towards a more individualized and on-demand experience. To address these consumer considerations, I plan to adopt and adapt approaches to engaged different learning styles as outlined in the VARK (visual, aural, read/write, kinesthetic) framework. By addressing various audiences within their preferred environments, I will be able to more effectively connect with the students to enhance their learning experience. Furthermore, I plan to be more expansive by employing framework that is inclusive additional learning styles as found in the nine intelligences. These styles include existential intrapersonal, interpersonal, kinesthetic, linguistic, logical, musical, naturalistic, and visual. There is typically no single standalone learning style, but a primary set of preferences. These preferences can be clustered into a combination of various styles, which tend to be topic and situationally influenced. The endgame to this approach is to provide a variety of learning opportunities through self-selected learning styles paths while introducing other paths to cross-pollenate and help students engaged in different ways of learning. The overarching goal of setting up this learning environment is to broaden student perspectives while strengthening and expanding their knowledge and skills.

The associated learning material and resources for the online course will include short-clip-it videos that provide summaries, cases studies, and technical descriptions with examples. Other learning materials will include articles, case assessments, written materials, step-by-step directions, graphics, infographics, and exploratory activities which will require the students to move (e.g., interview, research, and explore various concepts and information). This strategy will provide opportunities for students consume and obtain or strengthen insight through VARK and the intelligences. The arrangement of these materials will be constructed in a seamless layout, which will apply a complementary and sequential introduction and reinforcement process. This cyclical approach will be braided throughout the entire class and program pathways and align with the program outcomes. In addition, the design of the online course room will be created with universal design practices that will be applied in a dynamic way that learning can be achieved on various devices (e.g., mobile phone, tablet, laptop).

Another approach to facilitate knowledge building will be conducted through experiential learning where scenarios will require students to apply critical skills (e.g., synthesis, critical

assessment, communication). Constructivism practices will be displayed by establishing cross-functional teams that will operate autonomously from me to respond to situations. By creating these independent student teams, it will require them to leverage their collective experience to support each other to reach a common objective. Additional student-to-student interaction will occur in the discussion and announcement boards, which will require various discussion types (e.g., written, video, voice recording, infographics) to be created and shared. Feedback will go beyond the standard affirmation response in a discussion post but provide deep inquiry to perspective to build insight and help students validate their position, perspectives, and recommendations. Other skills that will be expressed will include plan development, collaboration, compromise, and project management. Accountability will be blending across these peer assessments will consist of formative and summative feedback.

A graphical representation of this approach provides the intersection of various consideration to have when developing a relevant and engaging online learning environment.

By developing online courses utilizing a combination of these frameworks and provide a variety of ways to engages students across varying levels of information consumption and learning. Moreover, this will foster a more inclusive learning environment.

III. DISCUSSION

Through the review of literature, combined with a personal reflection of participation in multiple faculty onboarding programs, and experience teaching across different instructional modalities within higher education has broadened my perspective for the development of online courses to meet student where they are. This perspective is not just literally meeting students in a virtual environment anytime or anywhere, but in the sense where learning can be engaged through different instruction and facilitation approaches. It is recommended that instructors that are seeking to adapt their onsite course(s) to an online environment or want to strengthen their online courses consider the various approaches and learning environments that address the cognitive diversity of their current and future students or participants.

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